

MINING FOR LUNAR HELIUM-3: A MISCONCEPTION ROOTED IN FALSE FUSION MYTHOLOGY. R.A. Bamford¹ and B. Bingham¹ ¹RAL Space, STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Harwell Campus, Didcot, Oxfordshire, OX11 0QX, U.K. (ruth.bamford@stfc.ac.uk)

Introduction: The idea of mining Helium-3 (³He) on the Moon is often promoted as a future energy solution, linking lunar resource extraction with clean, limitless fusion power on Earth. However, this vision stems from a fundamental misunderstanding of both nuclear fusion physics and the current state of fusion energy technology. This paper outlines why ³He fusion is technologically unfeasible and scientifically misguided compared to realistic fuel cycles like deuterium-tritium (D-T) and deuterium-deuterium (D-D).

³He-based fusion, especially the ³He-D reaction, requires significantly higher plasma temperatures and more stringent confinement conditions than D-T fusion, yet offers much lower fusion cross-sections. Any meaningful ³He reactor would still depend on deuterium, and inevitably lead to side reactions producing tritium and neutrons—negating claims of it being aneutronic.

The Myth of Clean Helium-3 Fusion

In Physics World, Prof Frank Close [1] critically examines the origins of the ³He fusion myth. He explains that despite the appeal of a neutron-free fusion option, D-³He fusion is up to 100 times less efficient than D-T fusion due to the higher Coulomb repulsion between the nuclei. Fusion in devices like tokamaks involves a well-mixed plasma, not particle-beam-like collisions. As a result, deuterium in the fuel mix inevitably fuses with itself to produce tritium, which then reacts with deuterium in the standard D-T pathway—generating the very neutrons ³He fusion was supposed to avoid.

Suggestions to use ³He-³He fusion are even more implausible. The reaction cross-section is lower still, and the required plasma conditions are beyond what even ITER is designed to achieve. As Close puts it, the lunar helium-3 narrative is “moonshine”—a captivating but physically baseless proposal.

Fusion Fundamentals

Figure 1 is crucial—it shows the fusion reactivity, or the probability of a reaction occurring, as a function of plasma temperature. The temperature is plotted on a logarithmic scale in billions of kelvin, highlighting one of the central challenges of fusion: achieving and sustaining these extreme conditions, far beyond what any known material can contain. This is why magnetic confinement (as in tokamaks) or inertial confinement (as with lasers) is essential—to hold and control the hot plasma without physical contact.

Figure 1. The key plot that shows why D-T is so much more achievable than D-He3. He3-He3 is literally off the chart.

Fusion power development is focused on fuel cycles that offer the best chance of achieving energy breakeven and beyond. The D-T reaction:

has the highest reaction rate at attainable plasma temperatures (~100 million K), forming the foundation of ITER and NIF projects. D-D fusion, while neutron-producing, is also under investigation for longer-term viability.

In contrast, the $D + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}^4\text{He} + p + 18.3 \text{ MeV}$ reaction occurs at lower rates and higher temperatures. Moreover, D-D side reactions in any ³He plasma will inevitably regenerate the D-T pathway.

Consider the proposed $D + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow p + \text{He}$, as the reaction as it is little easier than pure ³He+³He which is literally off the chart of Fig.1.

As Figure 1. Shows the D-D will occur more readily than the D-³He or ³He-³He.

Means you get back to the original fusion approach of D-T.

Therefore even assuming a functioning D-³He reactor, deuterium's unavoidable D-D reactions lead to neutron production.

Some designs propose lithium blankets to breed tritium via:

Such schemes reinforce the reality that any fusion reactor must still manage neutron fluxes, radiation shielding, and tritium logistics.

Why Particle Collisions Don't Work

Fusion is not pursued by particle accelerators, where beams of nuclei collide head-on, because they are inherently inefficient for NET energy generation. A useful analogy: if a hydrogen atom were scaled to the size of the solar system, the nucleus would be a Neptune-sized object at the centre, with the electron orbiting at Neptune's distance. Trying to hit two such "nuclei" head-on would be like smashing two Neptunes together with exact precision across solar distances. Instead, fusion occurs statistically within a hot plasma—a mix of fully ionised nuclei and electrons—where electromagnetic forces dominate.

Because the probability of fusion decreases with increasing particle velocity, the effective cross-section for head-on collisions becomes vanishingly small at higher speeds.

Why a plasma

Instead, fusion relies on the collective behaviour of a dense, hot plasma where billions of nuclei interact statistically. These nuclei are held together by a surrounding cloud of fast-moving electrons, which help shield the positive charges from each other, making occasional fusion events possible despite strong Coulomb repulsion.

The Lawson Criterion and Fusion Conditions

Achieving net energy output from fusion requires satisfying the Lawson criterion: high enough plasma density (n), temperature (T), and confinement time (τ). The so-called "triple product" ($nT\tau$) sets a minimum threshold for ignition. D-T is currently the only fusion reaction within reach of meeting this requirement.

To produce net energy, a burning plasma is needed—where fusion reactions sustain themselves. In D-T fusion, a short-lived ^3D intermediate quickly decays, releasing energy mostly into heating surrounding ions. Attempting this with ^3He requires conditions far beyond existing materials and technologies.

Practical and Technical Challenges

^3He fusion would demand plasma temperatures and confinement far exceeding those in current reactors. No known material or confinement system can withstand these conditions. After 70 years of research, we have only just begun approaching viable conditions for D-T fusion, as in JET (magnetic confinement)[2] and NIF (laser-driven inertial confinement)[3].

Why No Fusion Power Stations Yet?

Fusion is happening routinely in experiments like JET and NIF, but not yet at a scale where the net energy output exceeds the total energy input to the

whole system—particularly including all the support infrastructure.

Fusion experiments typically operate at plasma temperatures *far higher* than those at the core of the Sun. While the Sun achieves fusion via low-rate reactions sustained over vast volumes and immense gravitational pressure, laboratory fusion requires extreme energy densities and confinement.

The Sun gets away with slower reaction rates due to its enormous size and stable conditions, but terrestrial reactors must achieve much higher temperatures and confinement times to compensate. Practically, this leads to major engineering challenges: not only the "first wall" problem—developing materials that can survive intense neutron bombardment and thermal stress—but also fundamental plasma physics problems. Hot plasmas are prone to turbulence and instabilities, and they lose energy through mechanisms like bremsstrahlung radiation, which saps power from the plasma in the form of X-rays.

Clarifying the Narrative

The persistence of ^3He fusion in lunar discourse reflects a wider gap between scientific literacy of other disciplines and enthusiasm. As researchers, it's important we clarify rather than dismiss. The Moon holds genuine promise: for planetary science, ISRU, and infrastructure development. But energy for Earth will not come from mining ^3He .

Moreover, ^3He is rare even on the Moon. It is dispersed in low concentrations within the regolith, making its extraction, processing, and transport a logistical and economic burden—if it were even needed, which current science says it is not.

Conclusion: The Moon's True Value

The Moon is vital to the future of exploration, science, and sustainability—but not as a source of terrestrial fusion fuel. Technologies enabling ISRU and subsurface access serve practical missions and long-term infrastructure goals. Once terrestrial fusion is achieved, it will become a transformative power source—enabling human settlement across space, where nearly every function depends on reliable energy.

As we approach a new era of lunar exploration with Artemis and international missions, and as prototype fusion plants emerge, it is essential that we ground our ambitions in scientific reality—not in alluring myths.

References: [1] Close, F. *Physics World* 20, no. 8 (2007): 16. [2] Čufar, A., et al. *Fusion Science and Technology*, 74(4), 370–386. [3] Abu-Shawareb, H., et al. *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 132, no. 6, 2024, p. 065102.